

Islanded Microgrids control by using Grid Former and Synthetic Slack Bus concept - A preliminary analysis

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Abstract— Microgrids are electrical entities which will be more frequent in areas with high penetration of renewable energy sources. Consequently, it is an increasing need for reliable tools appropriate for load-flow and dynamic analysis, especially for the off-grid operation. However, simulation compatibility for on-grid operation must be also available. In addition, microgrids are by their nature weak systems: some loads may be comparable with generation units, which are also divided into grid former and grid followers. In this paper, a preliminary assessment of such microgrids is made, based on load-flow analysis on a Quasi-Steady Static Time Series and a Synthetic Slack Bus concept. These are used to obtain realistic results and appropriate deployment solutions for independent microgrids operation.

Index Terms — Microgrid, Grid Former, Synthetic Slack Bus

I. INTRODUCTION

Microgrids (μG) are networks geographically spread over limited area, which consist of loads, generators, and storage assets, that are coordinated by means of local intelligence [1][2]. The microgrids are entities that will become more present in an environment with high renewable energy sources (RES), under increased requirements for resilience of the local energy community. The power system engineers need, therefore, powerful tools for analyzing microgrids under both steady-state and dynamic operation, in either grid-connected or islanded (off-grid) operation. If time-based analysis of off-grid microgrids is required, acceptable results can be obtained with tools such as Simulink, however with an increased computational burden and a limited time window analysis.

In large power systems, the biggest power plants, which can maintain appropriate active and reactive power reserves to balance the system, are usually taken as slack bus. However, in small off-grid electrical networks, small and many in number distributed generators exist, which cannot be individually considered as slack bus. Under these conditions, load-flow calculation, which assumes perfect balance between generation and load, based on one slack bus is no longer possible. Therefore, several slack busses might be necessary, which bring additional complications in taking the reference phase angle

and performing the load-flow calculation. On the other hand, there are difficulties in choosing appropriate load models, as there is no guarantee that a P-Q or a Z model reflects the real nature of the loads, as each load may have a different behavior. This latest aspect is not easy to be simulated even in time-based analysis. All these elements require some adaptations from the classic load-flow analysis and therefore need a different approach to achieve acceptable results. These challenges are addressed in detail in [3], while an important contribution is on the modeling techniques, from EMTP to envelope-based techniques, where quasistatic phasor calculus is considered as a simplified version of dynamic phasor calculus, which can be approached through Quasi-Static Time Series (QSTS) [4]. This paper analyzes some of these new aspects and proposes a new approach valid for weak independent (islanded) microgrids.

The purpose is to address the following challenges:

- to find an appropriate substitute of the traditional slack bus by introducing the “synthetic slack bus” (SSB) to be applied in islanded microgrids; the intention is to extend and detail concepts presented in [3].
- for achieving the SSB functionality, instead of a classic slack bus, an ideal voltage source (VS) with series impedance is proposed, also incorporating the specific control for implementing a SBB function. Moreover, there is potential to use VS for other grid elements as well, e.g., for multi-SB setups.
- in order to test the characteristics of this approach by using load-flow (LF) sequences for building QSTS. The chosen LF tool is OpenDSS, originally designed for distribution grids, which can use voltage sources and QSTS.
- the approach proposed in this paper is also intended to be used for easy design and deployment in real equipment, such as in the control algorithm of the inverter, which will act as grid former of the off-grid network, and which can implement the SSB concept.

A detailed study has been performed for a subset of scenarios, specific to a μG running only on power-electronic interfaced (PEI) generation units, with operation which is not dependent on the grid frequency.

The microgrid is assumed symmetrical, on both generation and load, which allow analyzing the three-phase network through a single-phase one.

II. METHODOLOGY

Microgrids can work on-grid, usually connected to the main grid via one point of common coupling (PCC), or off-grid, when their intelligence needs to be used for various functionalities, among which the most challenging is the real-time generation-load balancing. This functionality is usually supported by the main grid when the microgrid is connected to it. However, in the off-grid mode, predefined operation, either grid forming or grid following (or grid sustainers) is required [5][6] for the participating generators is chosen.

Due to the nature of microgrid, usually there is only one grid former. However, the rating of this main generator is usually small compared to the microgrid needs and its capability limits can be easily reached. For this reason, in general, using the slack bus concept, which is assumed to be of infinite power, is not suitable for load flow calculation. As a practical approach, a battery with its associated bidirectional power converter can be set as the grid former, i.e. the battery injects power into the AC grid when the converter operates in inverter mode, and absorbs power when it operates in rectifier mode, such that to ensure the generation-load balancing at any time instant. In networks with PEI generation only, the grid former also has the duty to control the system frequency, as well as to ensure the frequency stability as a substitute of the missing rotating masses from the synchronous machines, specific to the classic power systems. However, the aspects of zero inertia of PEI-based microgrids is not the subject of this paper.

In a paradigm of high-RES penetration, other generators are also connected to the network. Usually, they are acting as "grid followers", meaning that they synchronize their output with the frequency controlled by the grid former and inject power according with a P-Q or P-U model. Some of these inverters may be comparable in power with the grid former, thus being a good candidate to become one of the dominating grid nodes, with free P and Q limits, while U and θ is given by the grid steady-state conditions, with θ sliding continuously during time to cope with the network conditions. While choosing a slack bus (SB) is not an easy task in classic networks, in microgrids this may be even more difficult because the generators are comparable in power. In addition, when implementing a grid former - the best candidate for the SB, there is also a problem in simulating, testing and implementing this functionality in a comprehensive full chain which fits with each above phase.

Still, it is necessary to utilize a modelling approach that can also reflect the actual (physical) implementation of a device that acts like a slack bus. The paper analyzes this possibility by using a voltage source (VS) in series with its impedance, an equivalent which is also mentioned in [3]. A modern power electronics-based converter may have such an equivalent and can be operated - as the paper will demonstrate, to become in its point of common coupling (PCC) with the grid an equivalent of a slack bus. Figure 1a shows a microgrid connected in a PCC with such a VS. If VS is keeping constant the amplitude U_{VS} and its angle $\theta = 0$, then it acts as a SB. Figure 1b indicates a more realistic approach, with a VS having in series an

impedance Z_{VS} , however - without control, it is not acting as SB in the PCC anymore.

Fig. 1. Microgrid connected to a) an ideal Slack Bus/node; b) a implementable solution with a voltage source in series with its "internal impedance"

To see how to control a VS in series with its impedance (VSSI) - acting as a grid former of a microgrid, in order to emulate an SB in PCC, we will first analyze the following two cases, presented also in Figure 2:

- a VSSI which exchanges at a certain moment a specified P and Q with a SB having as per its definition a fixed $U_{SB} = U_{Setpoint}$ and $\theta(U_{SB}) = 0$ (Figure 2a);
- a VSSI which keeps at its PCC with the μG the same $U_{Setpoint}$ and $\theta(U)=0$ in such a way that the power $S = P + jQ$ through its impedance is the power absorbed by the μG for the given PCC values, as it can be deduced from its load-flow calculation with traditional U- θ , P-U and P-Q approach (Figure 2b).

Figure 2 shows the two subsystems (a and b), which can be considered equivalent at any moment with the complete system from Figure 2c.

Fig. 2. Equivalence between 1) two separated entities: a) VSSI connected to SB and b) μG connected to SB and 2) VSSI connected to μG through an PCC with the same SB setpoints (c).

In fact in Figure 2c the right-side exchange P and Q of the μG , as obtained from usual PF having the PCC acting as SB, while left side of PCC can be regulated as per exchanging with a SB the same P and Q. The two sides are therefore decouplable and can studied separately, with the only conditions being that:

- the PCC works like an SB and has consequently $U_{SB} = U_{Setpoint}$ and $\theta(U_{SB}) = 0$ for both parts, even if the left and right parts do not need to see and know about each-other;
- the right part (the microgrid) is deducting P and Q exchanged with PCC (the SB) as per its usual PF calculation.
- the left part (the VSSI) is regulated such that it can exchange the above P and Q with the PCC which is acting as a SB. The VSSI is practically sustaining all the time, through its control automation loop, the PQ exchange at the PCC, thus emulating a *Synthetic Slack Bus* (Syn-SB or SSB).

As being decouplable, the paper will first treat the VSSI left part to show the needed automation which can simulate the Sys-SB. This is made in the general situations, then will be treated the following particular situations: a) exchange of reactive power only; b) exchange of active power only. When designing converters, the reactance X can be considered as a cumulated effect of different series reactance used in the inverter design (e.g. for PWM frequency attenuation at the output), while R is requested to be as small as possible, to increase the inverter efficiency through decreasing losses. A simplified assessment will be given therefore in this paper, with the impedance having $R=0$ and by considering only X as being significant: $Z_{VS} = jX_{VS}$, which means $Z_{VS} = X_{VS}$. The general situation is presented below, starting from Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Grid former scheme for acting as a SSB.

Primary equations are as follows:

$$\underline{U}_{PCC} = \underline{U}_{VS} - \underline{Z}_{VS} \underline{I}_{VS} \quad (1a)$$

$$\underline{S}_{PCC} = \underline{U}_{PCC} \underline{I}_{VS}^* \quad (1b)$$

$$\underline{Z}_{VS} = R_{VS} + jX_{VS} \quad (1c)$$

Equation (1a) can be written by putting into evidence the real and imaginary part of each component and by using (1c):

$$U_{PCCRe} + jU_{PCCIm} = U_{VSRe} + jU_{VSIm} - (R_{VS} + jX_{VS})I_{VS} \quad (2)$$

The aim of this demonstration is to obtain U_{VSRe} and U_{VSIm} as a function of the other parameters. The following simplifications can be also made:

- R_{VS} can be neglected, as the internal impedance is considered to be mainly an inductive one: $Z_{VS} \approx jX_{VS}$ (2a)
- the node in PCC is intended to be a "slack bus" thus the θ angle of \underline{U}_{PCC} is $\theta = 0$, thus $U_{PCCIm} = 0$. In this context, the phasor \underline{U}_{PCC} has only real part, which is equal with the module U_{PCC} :

$$\underline{U}_{PCC} = U_{PCCRe} = U_{PCC} \quad (3)$$

In this situation, equation (2) can be written:

$$U_{PCCRe} = U_{VSRe} + jU_{VSIm} - jX_{VS} * I_{VS} \quad (4)$$

and by introducing the expression of I_{VS} from formula (1b) one can get $I_{VS} = \underline{S}_{PCC}^* / \underline{U}_{PCC}^*$ and by considering (3):

$$U_{PCC} = U_{VSRe} + j * U_{VSIm} - j * X_{VS} * \frac{P_{PCC} - jQ_{PCC}}{U_{PCC}} \quad (5)$$

By multiplying the whole equation with U_{PCC} we get

$$(U_{PCC})^2 = U_{PCC}U_{VSRe} + jU_{PCC}U_{VSIm} - jX_{VS}P_{PCC} + X_{VS}Q_{PCC} \quad (6)$$

We can get a system of two equations by separating the real and imaginary terms, and following relations are deduced:

$$\begin{cases} U_{VSRe} = U_{PCC} - X_{VS}Q_{PCC}/U_{PCC} \\ U_{VSIm} = X_{VS}P_{PCC}/U_{PCC} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

By drawing the phasors of current and voltages as well as P and Q at the PCC we can have representations such as the following two:

Figure 4: The general case, with $P_{PCC} \neq 0$ and $Q_{PCC} \neq 0$

where α is the angle of \underline{U}_{VS} , considering that \underline{U}_{PCC} has angle zero (as being considered a slack bus with $\theta=0$).

We can get then the parameters of the voltage source from cartesian to polar coordinates:

$$\begin{cases} U_{VS} = \sqrt{U_{VSRe}^2 + U_{VSIm}^2} \\ \tan(\alpha) = \frac{U_{VSIm}}{U_{VSRe}} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

and have with (7) and (8) the equations to obtain U_{VS} and α of the voltage source for the general case.

If the system requests in the PCC only reactive power, meaning $Q_{PCC} \neq 0$ and $P_{PCC} = 0$, the formulas (7) and (8) can be written:

$$\begin{cases} U_{VSRe} = U_{PCC} - X_{VS}Q_{PCC}/U_{PCC} \\ U_{VSIm} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{yields } \begin{cases} U_{VS} = U_{PCC} - X_{VS}Q_{PCC}/U_{PCC} \\ \tan(\alpha) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The phasors construction for Q_{PCC} negative and positive can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The particular case with $Q_{PCC} \neq 0$ and $P_{PCC} = 0$

If the system requests in the PCC only active power, meaning $P_{PCC} \neq 0$ and $Q_{PCC} = 0$, the formulas (8) and (9) can be

$$\text{written: } \begin{cases} U_{VSRe} = U_{PCC} \\ U_{VSIm} = X_{VS}P_{PCC}/U_{PCC} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{yields } \begin{cases} U_{VS} = U_{PCC} \sqrt{1 + X_{VS}^2 \frac{P_{PCC}^2}{U_{PCC}^4}} \\ \tan(\alpha) = X_{VS} \frac{P_{PCC}}{U_{PCC}^2} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

By introducing the second equation of (12) in the first one, we can get:

$$U_{VS} = U_{PCC} \sqrt{1 + \tan(\alpha)^2} = \frac{U_{PCC}}{\cos(\alpha)} \quad (13)$$

so (13) can finally be written:

$$\begin{cases} \tan(\alpha) = X_{VS} \frac{P_{PCC}}{U_{PCC}^2} \\ U_{VS} = \frac{U_{PCC}}{\cos(\alpha)} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

while the typical phasors combinations for $P_{PCC} > 0$ and for $P_{PCC} < 0$ can be seen in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: The particular case with $P_{PCC} \neq 0$ and $Q_{PCC} = 0$

Calculations in simulations and real implementations can consider the following inputs:

- active power exchange (wanted/requested by μG): P_{Exch}
- reactive power exchange (wanted/requested by μG): Q_{Exch}
- voltage in PCC (measured, given or wanted): U_{PCC} , while considering $\theta = 0$ as a general reference angle.
- reactance in series with the ideal voltage source: X_{VS}

III. VERIFYING ON A TEST CASE MICROGRID

To assess the challenges and the feasibility, a simplified test grid is chosen, which is analyzed by using a sequence of power flows, using QSTS technique. QSTS is already applied in several other studies [10][11].

The grid is practically seen on the right side of the "synthetic slack bus", which is kept with its U - θ characteristics by a grid former device modeled by the ideal voltage source behind a reactance X , as per Figure 2-c.

By applying the formulas detailed in the previous chapter, a specific active and reactive power (P_{Exch} and Q_{Exch}) can be exchanged with the slack bus by setting the values U_{VS} and α according to formulas (13) and (14). It shows in fact that the grid former can control in such a way its VS parameters that it can absorb or inject any P or Q, at an imposed voltage magnitude and phase, thus being able to replace the slack bus and to finally have the same effect on a grid (or microgrid) by controlling the U and alpha parameters of a VS behind the reactance X. It means that instead of exchanging power with a slack bus, SB can be removed and instead of it one can have a microgrid which is exchanging power in a similar way with the grid former, with its PCC node keeping voltage and angle fixed, as per slack-bus behavior.

Fig. 7 presents the studied test grid, having the grid former - acting as a generator or consumer, based on the power balance of the whole grid, an additional generator modeled as P-Q generator and a P-Q load are making the simplified network. The simplified analysis considers also that all connecting lines have a much bigger resistance than reactance, thus being in the situation of the so-called "resistive network" ($Z=R$), which is a quite usual simplification for studying LV networks.

Fig. 7. Analysed grid

If the grid former has the proper automation to keep in PCC (node N5 in the Figure 3) the $U=ct.$ and $\theta=0$, no matter the requirements of the grid to which is connected, then it becomes a *Synthetic Slack Bus*. In contrast to a theoretical slack bus, the synthetic slack bus keeps the SB characteristics by automation algorithm - which can be implemented with real power electronics, and not by a natural property of a theoretical SB.

This approach has the advantage of opening the window for dynamic studies by using a cascade of quasi-static states time series (QSTS) calculated with a load-flow program. Moreover, between the states, algorithms such as the Syn-SB functionality can be applied. If some algorithms employed between the QSTS's are time dependent, a bridge with real-time dynamic studies can be as well obtained. This paper remains however in the domain of non-time dependency between QS states, thus keeping the original QSTS definition from [2].

In order to assess the feasibility of the algorithm, the load profile of the load connected to N2 has been changed during each step of the time series, having a generic time step ΔT_{Step} which might be considered as being e.g. 1 second, compatible to the minimum QSTS step described in [2]. In our study this value is not explicit, as the simplified algorithm used for Syn-SB is not time dependent, but only previous step dependent, thus ΔT_{Step} value is not fully relevant, different values being applicable if at each step it can be considered a Quasi-Static situation. After each load-flow it has been applied the algorithm of pursuing slack-bus characteristics ($U_{PCC}=ct, \theta=0$) by varying the values U_{VS} and α , thus expecting that in node N5 we can obtain during the whole time series a characteristic of U_{PCC} and its θ value which is similar to a slack bus, thus proving that it can be obtained a synthetic slack bus.

The following tools have been used in the simulation:

- OpenDSS load-flow program [7][8][9]; this LF program has already been successfully used in several other studies [12][13][14]. It also has implementation of voltage sources in the grid, thus allowing to make LFs using VS's.
- a dedicated, open-source application GMK [15] which is able to manage the User Interface (UI) of a targeted grid, to invoke OpenDSS for calculating grid values, to implement QSTS sequence and to perform the Syn-SB algorithm between every two LF calculations during the QSTS sequence. A view of the grid through GMK-UI, before starting the QSTS scenario, is presented in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. GMK-UI for the analysed grid, with initial powerflow from OpenDSS

In the *first scenario*, the PQ load placed in node N2 is changing both P and Q at each step. The active power P is increasing with 0.5 kW each step while the reactive power Q is decreasing with 0.2 kW each step, as per Figure 8. A number of 240 steps of the time series are sequenced, which bring P from initial value 0 to final value of 120 kW and Q from 0 to -48 kVAr. The evolution can be seen in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. P-Q evolution of the load in Scenario 1

In this scenario, the PV generator connected to node N4 and acting as a PQ generator has a fixed power $P_{PV}=50$ kW, with $Q_{PV}=0$ kVar. It means that until the load is reaching around 50 kW, there is an excess power in the grid which need to be absorbed by the synthetic SB (thus it acts as a consumer node), while when the consumption exceeds 50 kW - at the step $T(k)=100$, there is a need from the SSB to become generator and to cover the remaining power not delivered by the PV. The evolution of U and θ in PCC are presented in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. U_{PCC} and θ evolution at the grid former connection to the grid (N5)

It shows that the voltage module and angle follow the required values well in order to act as a slack bus, having a very small deviation of the voltage setpoint (less than 1 V, which is less than 0.5% error compared with the setpoint) and of the angle (less than 0.6 degrees error for the entire load evolution). While the main simulation is for fully resistive lines, a version with low $X/R=1/6$ is also shown in Figure 10, with a slightly different but very similar behavior of U and θ evolution in PCC.

While this paper deals with the SSB feasibility in a simplified manner (next step QSTS correction based on formulas 8-9), future work will focus on improving algorithms and increasing the accuracy for the SSB performance, including in dynamic regimes due to high level disturbances.

Figure 11 shows the evolution of VS parameters U_{VS} and α , according to the SSB control presented before. To keep the SSB parameters, the voltage level of VS needs to be controlled in the $[0.84 \dots 1.05]$ p.u. range, while the angle needs to have values between $[-12 \dots +28]^\circ$. Such information is useful for implementation design, addressed in section IV.

Figure 12 shows the power exchange in PCC during the entire 240 steps operation. It can be seen that the GF emulated by the controlled VSSI is absorbing power in the first part of the scenario - till the step marked by $T(k)=93$ (before step 100, due to the need to cover as well the grid losses of the resistive lines), then turns into generator, till the end of the scenario, while Q is always in consumption mode due to negative Q of the load coupled in N2.

Fig. 11. U_{VS} and α calculated control of the voltage source

Fig. 12. Power exchange between Grid Former and microgrid

The QSTS simulation with proposed Syn-SB algorithm shows good behavior in a wide range of load variation in the μG : P within $[0 \dots 120]$ kW and Q within $[0 \dots -48]$ kVar.

A *second scenario* has now a positive ramp for load's Q evolution, as seen in Figure 13.

Fig. 13. P-Q evolution of the load in Scenario 2

The evolution of the synthetically kept parameters at PCC, namely $U_{VS}=230.94$ V and $\theta=0$ can be seen in Figure 14. In this second scenario, the voltage level U_{PCC} is kept with a maximum error of 0.75% and the angle θ has a maximum error of -0.4° , which is only 0.4% from 90° . The QSTS simulation with proposed Syn-SB algorithm shows good behavior in a wide range of load variation in the μG : P within $[0 \dots 120]$ kW and Q within $[0 \dots 48]$ kVar for both resistive and low X/R lines.

Fig. 14. U_{PCC} and θ evolution at the grid former connection to the grid (N5)

Several other scenarios, not presented in this paper, shown similar behavior for the Syn-SB implementation.

IV. ASPECTS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF A GRID FORMER

One of the aspects pointed in the scope of this paper has been to show that the Syn-SB implementation can be deployed in real equipment, such as in the automation algorithm of the inverter which will act as grid former of an off-grid network. Figure 15 shows such a possible implementation.

Fig. 15. Grid former implementation

One can see that implementing a Syn-SB is feasible with a GF having the possibility to generate and absorb power from the grid, in a similar way in which a SB is doing in a load-flow calculation, by closing the power balance of the whole network. In the Syn-SB approach, the PQ balancing needs can be physically measured at a certain moment at the PCC by the GF, while the automation can change U_{VS} and α_{VS} such that the PCC has similar behavior with the theoretical SB ($U_{PCC} = U_{Setpoint} = ct.$ and $\theta=0$). By using the measured PQ exchange with the GF as inputs of the algorithm and by asking that PCC has a constant U and θ , GF can keep on PCC the behavior of a *Synthetic Slack Bus*, as being the border (PCC) between GF (left side in Figure 14) and microgrid (right side in Figure 14).

V. CONCLUSIONS

The paper analyzed microgrid behavior in a stand-alone off-grid operational status. Moreover, it introduced the concept of *Synthetic Slack-Bus*, which approximates a theoretical slack bus, obtained through control provided by the Grid Former device, by considering also the power exchange in its PCC.

An advantage of this approach is that there is a good correspondence between simulations which are using LF calculation within QSTS sequences - being able to also catch a dynamic behavior (otherwise needing complex tools for time-dependent analysis, such as with Simulink), while the simulated solution can also be more easily deployed in real equipment implementing a GF device, which can drive an independent microgrid. Moreover, the approach has roots for new directions regarding various subjects, that may include multi-GF architectures using multi-VS acting as Syn-SB's (a setup which is difficult usually to address with more than one SB). More general studies may consider in full the system parameters (R_{VS} in addition to X_{VS} , lines X in addition to their resistive part, asymmetrical regimes, increased accuracy, and optimized functions for performing SSB control etc.). As the Syn-SB uses

a default $\theta=0$, further analysis and control strategies of microgrids may consider angles orchestration between various VSs in the μG , using e.g. GPS synchronization when available. The approach also gives essential information for the bidirectional inverters design and in combination with their DC bus, opening also new possibilities for analyzing and controlling hybrid AC-DC architectures, considering e.g. that the DC bus and the PCC of the AC network can have a mutual influence which can be modelled during the QSTS sequences.

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